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COMPENDIUM OF PUBLISHED RESEARCHES IN BASIC EDUCATION

(2019 – 2021)

Manuel O. Tegerero
School Head/Editor-in chief

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Republic of the Philippines
DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION
Region VIII (Eastern Visayas)
Schools Division of Eastern Samar
DOLORES NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL
Dolores

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Certified correct;

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FOREWORD

The Dolores NHS Research and Innovation Journal (DRIJ) aims to publish teacher-researchers and students' articles on education, developments on educational policies, advancements on educational technologies, and other multi-disciplinary areas in basic education research under the research agenda of the Department of Education. Contributors have submitted their research abstracts and the details of their published papers following the technical format of the journal, and were reviewed and revised based on clarity, organization, language and length.

For the first time in the history of this humble public secondary education, the Dolores National High School has established its own ISSN-based research journal, as an affirmation of the publish or perish dictum. This issue covers a lot of innovation centered-researches that hopes to improve the mathematical performance of students. For instance, the team of Mr. Ben Fermin Q. Abuda managed to measure mathematics performance via the use of Strategic Intervention Material. Notably, Mrs. Glory Oraller-Balazo assessed struggling students mathematics performance using an enhanced electronic-based SIM.

Mr. Roselle Valerio Noroña focused on assessing schools laboratories and students' mastery level in science process skills, which is timely and relevant in today's PISA result of the country.

Mrs. Mischiel Gagate – Adigue gave light on the present status of the modular education in the lens of 4Ps – parents in her hometown.

In the area of teachers' professional development, Ms. Kareen Dionesia R. Rivera evaluated teachers training needs in the new normal, and found the need to upskill teachers on the use of 21st century-based pedagogies.

Mrs. Glady Cidro-Lagria conducted a fascinating qualitative undertaking on the challenges and coping practices of novice out-field teachers in English in the schools division of Eastern.

Lastly, an evaluation of students' numeracy competence and their senior high school readiness was presented by Mr. Jestoni C. Orque which provided insights on the readiness of junior high school completers to partake the last two years of their basic secondary education.

With this special issue, the Dolores National High School Research Office and the editorial Staff of the Dolores NHS Research and Innovation Journal push to emphasize the contribution of research to pedagogical knowledge, mastery level, and the professional development of 21st century educators in the new now.

Our snappy salute to the contributors to this issue!

The Editors

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MASTERY LEVEL OF STUDENTS USING STRATEGIC INTERVENTION MATERIAL (SIM) IN TEACHING MATHEMATICS: A QUASI EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

BEN FERMIN Q. ABUDA

Special Science Teacher 1

Abstract. This experiment focused on 11th Graders' mastery level using Strategic Intervention Material (SIM) based-instruction in General Mathematics least mastered competencies. Pre/posttest Quasi-experimental research was employed with two classes of 11th Graders from the Technical, Vocational and Livelihood (TVL) track were taught via SIM-based instruction and direct instruction, respectively. These learners took the subject amid the school year 2018-2019 and were tagged non-numerates in their previous mathematics class. To ensure proper maneuvering of the SIM and time-on-task, the teacher-researcher handled both classes at the same venue and time frame. The learners' pre/posttest mean scores served as basis in determining learners' mastery level while t-test analyses tested the pre-posttests' difference of the comparison groups. Findings revealed the posttest mean scores of SIM-group to be significantly greater than the DI-group, hence SIM-based instruction is an effectual means in reaching mastery on least mastered competencies in General Mathematics. Hence, it is recommended not to delimit Direct Instruction in upskilling least mastered competencies alongside with SIM-based instruction. Furthermore, SIM-based instruction can be implemented to other schools to supplement its effectiveness and to maximize its use in the future, and that studies on the use of SIM-based remedial instruction in other learning areas, be conducted to confirm the result of the experiment.

Keywords: Mastery Level, Strategic Intervention Material, Pre-test, Posttest

How to cite the actual paper:

Abuda, B.F. Q. (2019). Mastery level of students using Strategic Intervention Material (sim) in teaching mathematics: a Quasi-experimental study. *Instabright e-gazette*. 1[1]. <https://www.instabrightgazette.com/blog/mastery-level-of-students-using-strategic-intervention-material-sim-in-1715bb76-0780-40ea-bebb-1ca02d59e81c?categoryId=104981>

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STRATEGIC INTERVENTION MATERIAL (SIM) BASED INSTRUCTION'S EFFECT ON THE MATHEMATICS ACHIEVEMENT OF STUDENTS-AT-RISK-OF-DROPPING-OUT (SARDO)

BEN FERMIN Q. ABUDA, MARIEL CLARISSE CABILI, MA. FE ANGEILENE M. MAESTRE, GLORY FE ORALLER, JESTONI ORQUE

Teachers, Schools Division of Eastern Samar

Abstract. This study investigated the effect of a Strategic Intervention Material (SIM) on the achievement of Grade 11 students at risk of dropping out (SARDO) in General Mathematics. The study used experimental method of research through a single group pre-test/posttest design among SARDOs of Dolores National High School for the School Year 2018-2019. Pretest and posttest questionnaire involving solving rational equations were used as main instrument for data collection both before and after the experiment periods. Results indicated that there is highly significant achievement in the level of Grade 11 students' performance in solving rational equations applied through a SIM day Self-Paced Intervention Program. The study concluded that teaching students using SIM in a self-paced manner gives a high effect on students' learning. Hence, it recommends among others that a SIM-based instruction should be encouraged in schools and that teachers of all levels and disciplines be given training-workshop on theories and practice of SIM to address learning gaps in the academe.

Keywords: Strategic Intervention Material; Students-at-risk-of-dropping-out (SARDO); student' achievement; SIM day Self-Paced Intervention Program

How to cite the actual paper:

Abuda, B.F. Q., Cabili, M.C., Maestre, M.A.M., Oraller, G.F.O, & Orque, J. (2019). Strategic Intervention Material (SIM) based instruction's effect on the Mathematics Achievement of Students-at-risk-of- Dropping-Out (SARDO). *Instabright e-gazette*. 1[1]. <https://www.instabrightgazette.com/blog/strategic-intervention-material-sim-based-instruction-s-effect-on-the-82ddb7b-54c8-4579-b40f-e5f1a451af73?categoryId=104981>

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STRUGGLING LEARNERS' MATHEMATICS ACHIEVEMENT LEVEL USING QUICK RESPONSE EMBEDDED STRATEGIC INTERVENTION MATERIAL

**BEN FERMIN Q. ABUDA, MARIEL CLARISSE CABILI,
MA. FE ANGEILENE M. MAESTRE, GLORY FE ORALLER,
JESTONI ORQUE**

Teachers, Schools Division of Eastern Samar

Abstract. This study focused on the effect of a QR-embedded Strategic Intervention Material (QRSIM) on the achievement level of 11th Grade Students in General Mathematics via Solomon-four group research design, focusing on the least mastered competencies in solving exponential equations. A total of 120 students participated in the experiment at Dolores National High School during the school year 2019-2020. Findings revealed that; the students were unable to reach the expected level of achievement based on the pretest; the experimental and control groups with pretest performed better in the posttest assessment; no significant difference was observed between the pretest achievement level of the students; the pretest and posttest achievement levels of the experimental and control group shows a significant achievement; and that the achievement levels among the four groups significantly improved in the posttest. The findings of this study highlight the use of an innovative SIM based instruction and its counterpart in teaching frequently least mastered competencies in the subject, General Mathematics that paves the way in developing mathematical competencies among 11th grade learners. Furthermore, the researcher recommends that; assessing the learners' level of achievement prior to instruction will aid teachers in developing instructional tools and approaches suited to their scholastic needs; Mathematics teachers should be geared with appropriate knowledge on the use of 21st century teaching and learning resources such as Strategic Intervention Material to help a student who finds mathematics concepts difficult to comprehend; and that a similar study be conducted to cover other least learned competencies in the Eastern Samar division to further probe and enrich the findings of this study.

Keywords: Least Mastered Competencies, Solomon Four Group Design, Achievement Level, Pretest, Posttest

How to cite the actual paper:

Abuda, B.F. Q., Cabili, M.C., Maestre, M.A.M., Oraller, G.F.O, & Orque, J. (2019). Struggling learners' mathematics achievement level using Quick response embedded Strategic Intervention Material. *International Journal in Information Technology in Governance, Education and Business*, 1[1], 39-45. <http://www.ijitgeb.org/ijitgeb/article/view/11>

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ASSESSMENT OF SECONDARY SCHOOLS' READINESS TO NEW NORMAL AND HEALTH LITERACY OF TEACHERS IN THE COUNTRYSIDE AREA OF THE PHILIPPINES

BEN FERMIN Q. ABUDA¹, ROSELLE V. NOROÑA²

¹ *Special Science Teacher I*

² *Secondary School Teacher II*

Abstract. Health literacy affects a person's characteristics and exposure to various tools and mechanisms. However, there is insufficient research on the elements of school facilities and their impact on literacy. Hence, a descriptive-correlational study on health literacy and factors indicating schools' health readiness was conducted among senior high school teachers in Dolores National High School. This study's findings revealed that most senior high school teachers are female, young in the teaching profession, Master's degree holders, not exposed to medications, and have a high level of health literacy. Findings showed a significant moderate relationship between teachers monitoring practices and their communicative ($p = .016$) and critical health literacy ($p = .026$). Also, linear regression analyses revealed their length of service as the most significant predictor of health literacy level. Hence, it is recommended to develop a training design that will equip teachers in managing health issues among senior high school learners.

Keywords: Secondary schools, Health readiness, Health literacy, Senior high school teachers, Philippines

How to cite the actual paper:

Abuda, B.F. & Norona, R.V. (2020). Assessment of secondary schools' readiness to new normal and health literacy of teachers in the countryside area of the Philippines. *Countryside Development Research Journal*, 8[1], 15-23.
<https://cdrj.ssu.edu.ph/index.php/CDRJ/article/download/211/133>

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PREDICTIVE VALIDITY OF A CYBERCRIME AWARENESS TOOL: THE CASE OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN A PHILIPPINE SECONDARY SCHOOL

**BEN FERMIN Q. ABUDA, ROSELLE V. NORONA,
KAREEN DIONESIA, R. RIVERA**

Teachers, Schools Division of Eastern Samar

Abstract. The advent of technology paves for a better understanding of the various realities the world contains. However, misuse of these instruments' impacts people's way of living and education, especially in the new normal. Thus, an analysis was carried out to classify cybercrime awareness indicators as viewed by senior high school students at Dolores National High School using a researcher-developed unidimensional questionnaire. An 18-item Likert scale researcher-developed questionnaire, termed Cybercrime Awareness Tool (CcAT), was administered to a total of 200 students, with 50 respondents per senior high school strands using Google Form. The Principal Component Analysis (PCA) also known as Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was applied to the collected data which gave rise to four factors named; 1) Awareness on Phishing, 2) Awareness on Spamming, 3) Perceived effectiveness of antivirus software, and 4) Bullying on the web. The CcAQ was also found to have adequate internal consistency of .823 Cronbach alpha for the overall instrument, and subscale alphas ranging from .772 to .858. The multivariate analysis of variance on the interaction of sex and senior high school strand showed a significant link to the respondents' cybercrime awareness. Hence, the researchers recommend this tool to assess schools' cybercrime awareness on the four factors.

Keywords: Cybercrime Awareness, Exploratory Factor Analysis, Senior High School Strands

How to cite the actual paper:

Abuda, B.F. Q., Norona, R.V. & Rivera, K.D.R. (2020). Predictive validity of a Cybercrime Awareness Tool (CAT): The case of senior high school students in a Philippine secondary school. *International Journal in Information Technology in Governance, Education and Business*. 2[1] 18-26. <http://www.ijitgeb.org/ijitgeb/article/view/63>

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BARANGAY ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS READINESS AND EFFECTIVENESS ON DISTANCE LEARNING AS PERCEIVED BY 4PS PARENT-RECIPIENTS

BEN FERMIN Q. ABUDA¹, & MISCHIEL G. ADIGUE²

¹*Special Science Teacher 1*

²*Elementary School Teacher III*

Abstract. Continuity in education is a crucial task of the education sector in the time of pandemic. Thus, a study was made on the level of readiness and effectiveness on the implementation of distance learning among barangay elementary schools in Taft district, province of Eastern Samar during the school year 2020-2021. Using correlational research design, the researcher employed survey questionnaire among 100 4Ps' parents selected via total enumeration technique. The data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics at .05 level of significance. Findings revealed that the majority of the parent-recipient are earning a living through crop farming with a secondary level of education and that they belong to small family size. The barangay elementary schools are perceived to be highly ready and very effective in implementing distance learning. Notably, there is a significant negative association between parents' educational attainment and the perceived effectiveness of modular distance learning implementation, while a significant positive relationship between schools' readiness and effectiveness in implementing distance learning. Moreover, data revealed a significant difference in schools' readiness to implement distance learning. Hence, it is recommended for the Department of Education to provide a guidebook to parents that will enable them to assist their children in answering learning modules correctly, and to regularly review and monitor schools' learning continuity plans and to strengthen linkages with other stakeholders.

Keywords: Barangay Elementary Schools, Distance learning, Educational Attainment, Effectiveness, Readiness,

How to cite the actual paper:

Abuda, B.F. Q., & Adigue, M.G. (2021). Barangay elementary schools' readiness and effectiveness on Distance learning as perceived by 4Ps (Pantawid Familyang Pilipino Program) parent-recipient. *International Journal of teacher Education and Teaching*, 1[2]. 40-49. <https://ijtetchicago.files.wordpress.com/2021/09/july-2021-final-2.pdf>

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PRAGMATIC SENTIMENTS AND COPING STRATEGIES OF OUT-OF-FIELD ENGLISH TEACHERS IN PUBLIC SENIOR HIGH SCHOOLS

GLADY CIDRO - LAGRIA

Teacher II, Lalawigan National High School

Abstract. A phenomenological study was conducted to examine the challenges of out-of-field teachers in English, including their coping mechanisms and their suggested solutions to manage their sentiments in public senior high schools during the school year 2019-2020. The researcher used a one-on-one interview guide in collecting data, which were analyzed using the Ajjawi and Higgs framework of data analysis. The lack of content mastery that results in poor students' performance is the top sentiment for out-of-field teachers, and it was hard for them to teach English as it is out of their specialization. It was found out that the out-of-field teachers employed several coping strategies and suggested solutions to DepEd to manage their sentiments, such as; acquiring competence through training, self-learning and motivating, asking for assistance from co-teachers, and to improve schools' manpower. Hence, the researcher recommends the conduct of a comparative study on the performance of students and teachers, and regular mentoring of school heads and master teachers to aid out-of-field teachers. This calls for program mechanics that deal with alleviating the challenges that novice out-of-field teachers experience through program reforms, training and skills enhancement, professional development, and peer mentoring programs.

Keywords: Content Mastery, Competence, Manpower, Motivating, Self-Learning.

How to cite the actual paper:

Lagria, G.C. (2021). Pragmatic sentiments and coping strategies of out-of-field english teachers in public senior high schools. *International Journal of Qualitative Research*, 1[2], 112-119.
<https://ojs.literacyinstitute.org/index.php/ijqr/article/view/355>

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STRUGGLING LEARNERS' ACHIEVEMENT LEVEL USING ELECTRONIC STRATEGIC INTERVENTION MATERIAL IN MATHEMATICS (ESIMATH)

GLORY FE ORALLER - BALAZO

Special Science Teacher 1

Abstract. This study focused on the achievement levels of Grade 11 struggling learners using an electronic Strategic Intervention Material in Mathematics (eSIMath) in teaching least mastered competencies in the subject, Statistics and Probability for Senior High School. A Solomon four-group quasi-experimental research design was employed to two classes using eSIMath-based instruction, and two classes via conventional instruction, who were identified through a local diagnostic examination given by the teacher-researcher before the instruction for the second semester of the school year 2019-2020. The data gathered were analyzed using independent and dependent t-test, Dunnett's T3 test for post-hoc analysis of posttest scores, and assessment of mean gained scores. Findings of the study showed that the use of eSIMath-based instruction is an effective approach in the increase of struggling learners' achievement level in Statistics & Probability.

Keywords: Achievement Level, Conventional Teaching, Electronic Strategic Intervention, Material, Pre-test, Posttest

How to cite the actual paper:

Balazo, G.F.O (2021). Struggling learners' achievement level using Electronic Strategic Intervention Material in Mathematics (ESIMATH). *American Journal of Agricultural Science, Engineering and Technology*, 5[2], 207-214. <https://journals.e-palli.com/index.php/ajaset/article/view/96>

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STATUS OF LABORATORY RESOURCES AND SCIENCE PROCESS SKILLS OF GRADE 11 LEARNERS IN THE DIVISION OF EASTERN SAMAR, PHILIPPINES

ROSELLE V. NOROÑA

Secondary School Teacher II

Abstract. Instructional resources play a significant role in the development of man's scientific thinking. Thus, a hybridized descriptive correlational inquiry was conducted to examine the present availability and utilization statuses of science laboratory resources and the mastery level on integrated science process skills among 274 Grade 11 learners in three secondary schools in the division of Eastern Samar, Philippines. The data gathered from researcher-developed questionnaire on the availability and utilization status of basic science laboratory resources, and an adopted integrated science process skills test of Monica (2005) for the school year 2019-2020 were analyzed via frequency and percentage, median, Spearman rho, and Pearson r test of correlations. Findings revealed that there were only few available resources which were occasionally utilized in science instruction, while the 11th Grader-participants showed a very low mastery level on integrated science process skills. Also, a significant difference in terms of availability, utilization, and mastery levels existed among the three participating secondary schools in the division of Eastern Samar. Hence, it is recommended for the education sector to propose and develop a laboratory resource management system so that the availability and utilization of science instruments will be maximized, and an intervention program be provided among students to heighten their present integrated science process skills mastery level.

Keywords: Availability, Integrated Science Process Skills, Mastery Level, Science Laboratory Resources, Utilization

How to cite the actual paper:

Noroña, R. V. (2021). Status of laboratory resources and science process skills of grade 11 learners in the division of Eastern Samar, Philippines. *TARAN-AWAN Journal of Educational Research and Technology Management*, 2[1], 46-59.
<https://journal.evsu.edu.ph/index.php/tjertm/article/view/260>

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A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS ON THE STATUS OF LABORATORY RESOURCES AND SCIENCE PROCESS SKILLS OF GRADE 11 LEARNERS IN THE SCHOOLS DIVISION OF EASTERN SAMAR, PHILIPPINES

ROSELLE V. NOROÑA

Secondary School Teacher II

Abstract. This project-based study employed a comparative analysis in examining the present availability and utilization statuses of science laboratory resources and the mastery level on integrated science process skills among 274 Grade 11 learners in three secondary schools in the schools' division of Eastern Samar using a researcher-developed questionnaire on the availability and utilization status of basic science laboratory resources, and an adopted integrated science process skills test of Monica (2005) for the school year 2019-2020. Findings revealed a significant difference in terms of availability, utilization, and mastery levels among the three participating secondary schools in the schools division of Eastern Samar. Hence, it is recommended for the education sector to propose and develop a laboratory resource management system so that the availability and utilization of science instruments will be maximized, and an intervention program be provided among students to heighten their present integrated science process skills mastery level.

Keywords: Science Laboratory Resources; Integrated Science Process Skills; Mastery Level.

How to cite the actual paper:

Noroña, R.V. (2021). A comparative analysis on the status of laboratory resources and science process skills of Grade 11 learners in the schools division of Eastern Samar, Philippines *GNOSI: An Interdisciplinary Journal of Human Theory and Praxis*, 4[3], 137-147. <http://www.gnosijournal.com/index.php/gnosi/article/view/135>

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GAMIFIED TRACK-BASED REMOTE INSTRUCTION: ITS USE AND IMPACT ON MATHEMATICS COMPETENCE

BEN FERMIN Q. ABUDA, GLORY FE O. BALAZO

KAREEN DIONESIA R. RIVERA

Teachers, Schools Division of Eastern Samar

Abstract. The teaching of mathematics concerns difficulties, misconceptions, and challenges all wrapped into one, which pushed teachers for a personalized and direct instructional approach. However, with the loss of contact hours caused by the global pandemic, learners' mastery and competence on the subject matter are jeopardized. In this new normal, digitalized instruction and learning tools justify the continuity of education in any learning environment. Hence, a study examined the impact of a gamified track-based remote instruction on the level of competence of learners taking up Agri-Fishery and Home Economics strands in the Dolores National High School during the school year 2020-2021. The sequential-exploratory research design was undertaken, thereby collecting data such as selected participants' perceptions on the use of the proposed tool via focus group discussion during the piloting phase, assessment of learning gains during the quasi-experimental phase, and the determination of its impact on the participants' competence level using the identified four factors embedded on the extended Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) survey questionnaire. Findings showed that the use of a gamified track-based remote instruction enhanced the competency level of the two groups of participants. Also, out of the four factors, only self-efficacy was found to insignificantly predict participants' level of mathematics competence. Furthermore, the gamified track-based remote instruction can be implemented in other school and subject areas to supplement its effectiveness and maximize its use in the future.

Keywords: Gamified track-based Remote Instruction, Mathematics Competency, Senior High School Tracks

How to cite the actual paper:

Abuda, B. F. Q., Balazo, G. F. O., & Rivera, K. D. (2021). Gamified track-based remote instruction: Its use and impact on mathematics competence. *TARAN-AWAN Journal of Educational Research and Technology Management*, 2[1], 25-34.
<https://journal.evsn.edu.ph/index.php/tjertm/article/view/258>

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CORRELATION OF NUMERICAL COMPETENCE AND SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL READINESS OF GRADE 10 LEARNERS

JESTONI ORQUE

Secondary School Teacher III

Abstract. Equipping learners with ample numerical skills will enable them to face the challenges of the industrialized society. Hence, an investigation was conducted on numeracy competence, related factors, and senior high school readiness via a correlational research approach among 291 Grade 10 learners officially registered in four secondary schools in the Province of Eastern Samar, Philippines, during the school year 2019-2020. The results revealed that most of the highly numerate respondents preferred the Academic track over the Technical, Vocational, and Livelihood track. Track preference and senior high school readiness were all found to correlate significantly with respondents' level of numeracy competence; hence a new framework is developed. Thus, it is recommended among teachers to employ strategies that will strengthen learners' numerical readiness in acquiring relevant and contextualized information pertinent to the school setting. The research findings offer a viable framework for teachers to experiment with different approaches to teaching numeracy to students to increase their learning involvement and positive attitude toward mathematics.

Keywords: Correlation, Numeracy Competence, Readiness, Senior High School, Track Preference

How to cite the actual paper:

Orque, J. C. (2021). Correlation of numerical competence and senior high school readiness of grade 10 learners. *TARAN-AWAN Journal of Educational Research and Technology Management*, 2[1], 35-45. <https://journal.evsn.edu.ph/index.php/tjertm/article/view/259>

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PEDAGOGICAL PRACTICES AND MASTERY LEVEL IN MATHEMATICS AMONG SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS IN THE SCHOOLS DIVISION OF EASTERN SAMAR

KAREEN DIONESIA R. RIVERA

Secondary School Teacher III

Abstract. An investigation on the predictors of the 2018 National Achievement Test mastery level in mathematics as perceived by senior high school was done in the schools division of Eastern Samar. Using a researcher-modified instrument, the data were analyzed through descriptive statistics namely frequency count, percentage, median, and mode, while inferential statistics specifically multiple linear regression and spearman rho correlation analyses were used to ascertain the association of variables at 0.05 level of significance. Descriptively, results showed that majority of the respondents are fairly young female adult, graduated bachelors' degree, have attended regional training, have been awarded in the school/district level and achieved a very satisfactory rating in their individual performance and commitment review form covering the school-year 2017-2018. Also, the respondents' schools achieved low mastery levels in mathematics in the 2018 National Achievement Test. Moreover, the data revealed that most of the mathematics teachers practiced direct, indirect, and interactive instructions and perceived related factors to bear a significant impact on the mathematics performance of the schools. Using linear regression analysis, it was found that the teachers' educational attainment significantly predicts the schools' NAT results. Due to these findings, the researcher recommends that schools' administrators should encourage teachers to enroll in post-graduate programs and future researchers to conduct a similar study that will investigate external factors in a wider scope to provide a clear picture of the intricate factors affecting schools' mastery level in Mathematics.

Keywords: Mathematics, Mastery level, National Achievement Test, Educational Attainment, Pedagogical Approaches, Linear Regression Analysis

How to cite the actual paper:

Rivera, K.D.R. (2021). Pedagogical practices and mastery level in mathematics among senior high school teachers in the Schools Division of Eastern Samar. *Academia Letters*, Article 3337
<https://doi.org/10.20935/AL3337>

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APPROPRIATE PEDAGOGIES AND TRAINING NEEDS AMONG SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS IN THE NEW NORMAL: A COMPARATIVE STUDY

KAREEN DIONESIA R. RIVERA

Secondary School Teacher III

Abstract. In-service training programs in any organization enable employees to carry out their responsibilities concerning the organizations' standard and effective delivery. In the pandemic, there is an uprising concern among educators on how to deliver instruction and their readiness to do so. Hence, a descriptive-comparative approach was conducted to investigate senior high school teachers' readiness on developmentally appropriate pedagogies and their training needs. The data was collected using a researcher-developed electronic-based survey instrument thru Google Form among 35 senior high school teachers in Dolores National High School. The data analyses include mean computation in assessing respondents' level of academic competence, median for readiness on developmentally appropriate pedagogies and training needs, and non-parametric Mann Whitney U-test and Kruskal Wallis H-test on the significant difference of teacher readiness when compared according to their academic competence indicators. Findings revealed that the majority of the senior high school teachers possessed low academic competence, were exposed to developmentally appropriate pedagogies on teaching methods and modes of assessment, and needed immediate training in managing learners with multiple intelligences and learning styles, and provided instruction via electronic or distance learning mode. Also, results revealed a significant gap in the respondents' exposure to developmentally appropriate teaching methods compared to their training acquired ($p = .002$). Hence, the researcher recommends reviewing schools' in-service training and directs them in preparing senior high school teachers to deliver new-normal-based education.

Keywords: Training Needs, Readiness, Developmentally appropriate pedagogies

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Project PARIC

*“One School,
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Republic of the Philippines

Department of Education

Regional Office No. VIII (Eastern Visayas)

SCHOOLS DIVISION OF EASTERN SAMAR

Provincial Capitol Site, Bgy. Alang-alang, Borongan City, 6800

CERTIFICATE OF ACCEPTANCE

This certifies and acknowledges the receipt of a school-based Research Compendium consisting of completed and published research papers of the specified teacher-researchers/authors in the schools division of Eastern Samar.

Year of publication	Author(s)	Title of the study	Journal	Link (if available)
2019	Ben Fermin Q. Abuda	Mastery Level of Students using Strategic Intervention Material (SIM) in Teaching Mathematics: A Quasi Experimental Study	Instabright e-Gazette 1[1]	https://www.instabrightgazette.com/blog/mastery-level-of-students-using-strategic-intervention-material-sim-in-1715bb76-0780-40ea-bebb-1ca02d59e81c?categoryid=104981
2019	Ben Fermin Q. Abuda ¹ Mariel Clarisse Cabili ² Glory Fe O. Oraller ³ Jestoni C. Orque ⁴ Ma.Fe Angeilene Maestre ⁵	Strategic Intervention Material (SIM) based instruction's Effect on the mathematics achievement of students-at-risk-of-dropping-out (SARDO)	Instabright e-Gazette 1[1]	https://www.instabrightgazette.com/blog/strategic-intervention-material-sim-based-instruction-s-effect-on-the-82ddb7b-54c8-4579-b40f-e5f1a451af73?categoryid=104981
2019	Ben Fermin Q. Abuda ¹ Mariel Clarisse Cabili ² Glory Fe O. Oraller ³ Jestoni C. Orque ⁴ Ma.Fe Angeilene Maestre ⁵	Struggling learners' mathematics achievement level using Quick response embedded Strategic Intervention Material	International Journal in Information Technology in Governance, Education and Business, 1[1], 39-45.	http://www.ijitgeb.org/ijitgeb/article/view/11

Year of publication	Author(s)	Title of the study	Journal	Link (if available)
2020	Ben Fermin Q. Abuda ¹ Roselle V. Norona ²	Assessment of secondary schools' readiness to new normal and health literacy of teachers in the countryside area of the Philippines	Countryside Development Research Journal, 8[1], 15-23.	https://cdrj.ssu.edu.ph/index.php/CDRJ/article/download/211/133
2020	Ben Fermin Q. Abuda ¹ Kareen Dionesia Rivera ² Roselle Valerio Noroña ³	Predictive validity of a Cybercrime Awareness Tool (CAT): The case of senior high school students in a Philippine secondary school	International Journal in Information Technology in Governance, Education and Business 2[1] 18-26.	http://www.ijitgeb.org/ijitgeb/article/view/63
2021	Ben Fermin Q. Abuda ¹ Mischiel G. Adigue ²	Barangay Elementary Schools' Readiness and Effectiveness on Distance Learning as Perceived by 4Ps (Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program) Parent-Recipients	International Journal of teacher Education and Teaching, 1[2]. 40-49	https://ijtetchicago.files.wordpress.com/2021/09/july-2021-final-2.pdf
2021	Glady Cidro Lagria	Pragmatic sentiments and coping strategies of out-of-field english teachers in public senior high schools	International Journal of Qualitative Research, 1[2], 112-119.	https://ojs.literacyinstitute.org/index.php/ijqr/article/view/355
2021	Glory Fe Oraller - Balazo	Struggling Learners' Achievement Level Using Electronic Strategic Intervention Material In Mathematics (ESIMATH)	American Journal of Agricultural Science, Engineering and Technology, 5(2), 207-214.	https://journals.e-palli.com/index.php/ajaset/article/view/96
2021	Roselle Valerio Noroña	A Comparative Analysis on the Status of Laboratory Resources And Science Process Skills of Grade 11 Learners in The Schools Division of Eastern Samar, Philippines	GNOSI: An Interdisciplinary Journal of Human Theory and Praxis, 4(3), 137-147.	http://www.gnosijournal.com/index.php/gnosi/article/view/135
2021	Kareen Dionesia R. Rivera	Appropriate pedagogies and training needs among Senior High School teachers in the new normal: a comparative study	International Journal of Humanities and Innovation (IJHI), 4[4]	https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.33750/ijhi.v4i4.138

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2021	Roselle Valerio Noroña	Status of laboratory resources and science process skills of grade 11 learners in the division of Eastern Samar, Philippines: An Evaluation	TARAN-AWAN Journal of Educational Research and Technology Management, 2(1), pp.46-59.	https://journal.evsu.edu.ph/index.php/tjertm/article/view/260
2021	Ben Fermin Q. Abuda Kareen Dionesia Rivera Glory Fe O. Balazo	Gamified track-based remote instruction: Its use and impact on mathematics competence	TARAN-AWAN Journal of Educational Research and Technology Management, 2(1), pp.25-34.	https://journal.evsu.edu.ph/index.php/tjertm/article/view/258
2021	Jestoni C. Orque	Correlation of numerical competence and senior high school readiness of grade 10 learners.	TARAN-AWAN Journal of Educational Research and Technology Management, 2(1), 35-45.	https://journal.evsu.edu.ph/index.php/tjertm/article/view/259
2021	Kareen Dionesia R. Rivera	Pedagogical practices and mastery level in mathematics among senior high school teachers in the Schools Division of Eastern Samar	Academia Letters , Article 3337	https://doi.org/10.20935/AL3337

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2019

Dolores National High School

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Eastern Visayas State University, February 3-5, 2021

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University of the Philippines Manila, March 1-3, 2021

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Research Capability Status Report

INDICATORS	2019	2020	2021
1 No. of proposed action researches	2	0	2
2 No. of proposed basic researches	0	1	2
3 No. of funded action researches	2	0	1
4 No. of funded basic researches	0	1	0
5 No. of on-going action researches	0	0	1
6 No. of on-going basic researches	0	0	0
7 No. of completed action researches	0	2	0
8 No. of completed basic researches	0	0	1
9 No. of presented action researches	3	0	1
10 No. of presented basic researches	0	0	0
11 No. of DepEd funded/published education researches	0	0	1
12 No. of researcher-funded/published education researches	3	0	10
13 No. of awardees related to research	2	3	1
14 No. of conducted school-based research trainings	0	0	1

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School's Research & Ethics Committee

To ensure quality and acceptability of all proposals to be submitted to the SDRC, the following should be strictly implemented.

- 1 The school research secretariat shall receive electronic and printed copies of all proposed researches may it be an action or a basic research for possible funding under the schools MOOE or the basic education research fund, or the combination of both.
- 2 The secretariat shall check the contents of such proposals manually, and via Turnitin or Grammarly whichever is applicable and available.
- 3 The secretariat shall submit the proposal for a blind-peer review to check the conceptual and methodological sections of the proposal prior to endorsement to the SREC chair and vice chair.
- 4 The secretariat shall prepare the endorsement documents of the proposal prior its submission to the SDRC c/o division research coordinator.

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